

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF BAMBOO/PLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A number of bamboo reinforced plastic (BRP) composite materials have been developed, and the effects of matrix type and ply number on their properties investigated. Matrix types included epoxy, polylyte and urea formaldehyde, and tests were carried out to evaluate bending, impact, water immersion and fire resistance properties. Our data show that the longitudinal specific flexural strength and specific elastic modulus of bamboo/plastics are higher than those of glass/plastic and similar to mild steel. The elastic modulus however, decreases with increasing lamina number. Considering the bending characteristics of the three BRP types, it was found that bamboo/epoxy was excellent and bamboo/polylyte unsatisfactory, with bamboo/urea formaldehyde intermediate between the two. However, urea formaldehyde is cheap and its properties render it still suitable for domestic use. In terms of water and fire resistance, all the different types of BRPs tested were superior to wood.

The bamboo resource is abundant, and the cost of production of BRPs low. Consequently, we consider the application potential of this type of composite material to be immense.

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo is a natural composite material¹, being constituted from bamboo fibres (sclerenchyma cells) in a matrix of parenchyma cells, and possesses satisfactory mechanical properties for use in construction. There have been reports² on bamboo scaffoldings surviving better in a typhoon when compared to their steel counterparts. A number of investigations have been made on bamboo reinforced concrete, but because of the low flexural strength of bamboo and its poor bonding with concrete, the products have not been widely successful except perhaps in China. In contrast to timber trees which typically take 20 years to grow to harvestable size, bamboo plants only require 4 years, and grow in dense clusters. It is thus much cheaper than either wood or steel. However, its largescale application has been hindered by its cylindrical shape. It is an attempt to reach beyond this confine that bamboo reinforced plastics (BRPs) have been developed. BRPs can be moulded into different sizes and shapes to satisfy a variety of requirements, and the material is also resistant to bioerosion caused by insects and to cracking in dry weather. While many kinds of advanced composites with wide spectra of applications have been developed by reinforcing plastics with man-made fibres, e.g. S-glass, carbon, boron, kevlar, silicon carbide, etc.³, their production costs are high due to the costs of fibre fabrication. In contrast, natural fibres are easily available from jute⁴, palm, banana⁵, wood⁶ and bamboo⁷ and may be used readily as reinforcement for composites. This paper describes the formulation of bamboo reinforced plastics, and reports on their mechanical behaviour and resistance to fire and water. Comparative data have been obtained for over 200 specimens of various lamina numbers and matrix types.

FABRICATION OF BAMBOO/PLASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Material from the bamboo species *Bambusa paravariabilis* was cut longitudinally round the circumference in the internode region to produce sticks of length equal to the mould length. The sticks were passed between a pair of steel rollers which thinned down the material and partially separated the fibres from one another, to obtain strands approximately 1 mm thick.

Three types of resins were chosen for experimentation: epoxy, unsaturated polyester (polylite) and urea formaldehyde (U.F.). A Ciba-Geigy epoxy GY 257 and hardener HY 2958 (15% by weight) was used. For polylite, the hardener MEKP was about 12% by weight. In the case of urea formaldehyde, the aerolito 306 powder was dissolved in about 30% (by weight) of water, and 5% hardener added.

Two rectangular moulds were employed, with fibre arrangement in each either unidirectional [0] or bidirectional [0/90]. The prepacked mould was placed in a hot press, and a laminated composite of bamboo/plastic measuring 200 mm in length and 100 or 200 mm in width was formed. The number of layers varied from 1 to 10, and in some cases, bamboo sawdust was also used as filler and added to the mixture. The laminates were then cut into suitable dimensions for different tests (Table 1). All the data presented here are mean values for 3 to 6 specimens.

Table 1. The dimensions and processing conditions of bamboo/plastic specimens.

Matrix Type	Curing Temperature (°C)	Curing Time (min)	Pressure (MPa)	Dimension (mm)		
				Length	Width	Thickness
<u>Group A Specimens</u>						
Epoxy	95	25	2.5	150	10	0.8 - 8.6
Urea Formaldehyde	120	45	2.5	150	10	1.0 - 8.6
<u>Group B Specimens</u>						
Epoxy	100	25	1.4	200	25	9.0 - 10.0
Polylite	100	30	1.4	200	25	6.7 - 7.7
Urea Formaldehyde	125	45	1.4	200	25	5.4 - 8.0

FLEXURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BAMBOO/PLASTICS

Bending test is one of the main methods to evaluate the mechanical behaviour of load-bearing materials. The three-point bending test was used to determine the flexural properties of BRPs in this study. A typical load vs. displacement curve of a [0] specimen shows linear behaviour up to about half the fracture load (P_f), after which it is non-linear. This is a manifestation of the marked viscoelasticity of BRPs compared to carbon/epoxy [0] laminates, the latter normally having an inflexion point beyond three quarters of P_f . The presence of 2 inflexion points in the load-displacement curve (at 65 and 55% of P_f) shows that some bamboo laminates still sustained certain levels of local stress before ultimate brittle fracture.

Specimen failure occurs in a complex mode, and is related to lamina number. For unidirectional laminates of less than 5 laminae, fibres were partially expelled in the portion of the specimen subjected to tension, and subsequent brittle fracture occurred. For thick specimens with more than 5 laminae, the failure was due to formation and propagation of cracks at the fibre-matrix interface near the neutral axis. As thickness increased, maximum shear stress exceeded fibre-matrix bonding strength and delamination occurred. For cross ply laminates, failure was due to interface debonding and splitting of fibres in the transverse layers.

Table 2 shows the results of bending tests. Notably, the flexural strength

Table 2. Flexural properties of bamboo/plastic laminates (Group A specimens).

Type	Ply	Thickness (mm)	Flexural Strength σ_B (MPa)	σ_B/ρ	Elastic Modulus E_B (GPa)	E_B/ρ	Theoretical E_B (GPa)
<u>Bamboo/Epoxy</u>							
[0]	1	0.75	-	-	25.8	20.3	25.0
[0]	2	1.55	-	-	25.0	20.9	25.0
[0]	3	3.00	341	298	24.0	21.1	24.2
[0]	4	3.65	381	317	23.6	19.7	23.7
[0]	5	4.85	360	301	21.8	18.2	23.4
[0]	6	6.22	339	284	21.1	17.7	23.1
[0]	7	6.95	380	325	21.2	17.4	22.9
[0]	8	7.05	397	379	24.1	20.3	22.8
[0]	9	7.32	395	322	20.8	17.0	22.7
Mean:		5.58	370	318	23.0	19.2	23.6
[0/90]	3	3.60	254	234	22.6	20.8	23.4
[0/90]	5	5.37	243	214	15.8	14.2	18.7
[0/90]	7	7.40	164	153	12.3	11.5	16.5
[0/90]	9	8.60	198	181	11.1	10.2	15.3
Mean:		6.24	215	196	15.5	14.2	18.5
<u>Bamboo/Urea Formaldehyde</u>							
[0]	1	1.02	-	-	23.5	20.1	25.0
[0]	2	1.91	356	309	25.1	21.9	25.0
[0]	3	3.05	-	-	-	-	24.1
[0]	4	3.74	348	300	24.0	20.7	23.3
[0]	5	4.60	292	255	21.6	18.7	22.8
[0]	6	6.63	142	128	13.5	12.2	22.4
[0]	7	7.10	260	239	14.7	13.5	22.2
[0]	8	8.20	132	124	10.9	10.2	22.0
[0]	9	-	-	-	-	-	21.8
[0]	10	8.77	233	192	14.0	11.7	21.7
Mean:		5.00	252	221	18.4	16.1	22.9
[0/90]	3	2.90	157	155	17.4	16.7	23.1
[0/90]	5	5.75	164	156	12.1	13.6	18.6
[0/90]	7	7.35	82	81	7.6	7.3	15.0
[0/90]	9	9.44	77	72	5.7	5.4	13.7
Mean:		6.36	120	116	10.7	10.7	17.6
Epoxy:		5.10	-	-	4.4	3.3	-
Urea Formaldehyde:		5.60	-	-	1.2	1.0	-

(σ_B) and modulus (E_B) of [0] specimens is 10 to 15% higher than bidirectional specimens, but results varied according to laminae numbers. In general σ_B and E_B of epoxy composites were higher than U.F. composites, and flexural properties declined with increasing ply number. The addition of bamboo sawdust filler to bamboo/U.F. laminates reduced flexural strength (Table 3). However, the filler is cheaper than U.F., and the results in Table 3 show that a matrix containing 10% filler may be utilized without significant deleterious effects.

Table 3. The effects of bamboo sawdust filler on the flexural properties of Group A bamboo/urea formaldehyde 4 layered [0] laminates.

% Filler in Matrix	Elastic Modulus E_B (GPa)	Comparison Against Pure Matrix (%)	Flexural Strength σ_B (MPa)	Comparison Against Pure Matrix (%)
0	24.0	100	348	100
10	19.3	80	273	79
20	11.6	48	193	55
30	12.1	50	206	59

IMPACT TEST

Three point bending impact tests were performed using an impactor with a steel head of mass 4.5 kg, which could be set at different heights to vary the energy on impact. Test specimens were 200 mm long and 25 mm wide, and the thickness varied from 5.6 to 9.8 mm, depending on laminae number. The loading span was 180 mm, and drop height increased by 1 cm intervals from 1 cm upwards. The drop height at failure was recorded, and the energy absorbed calculated and presented in Table 4.

Table 4. The results of impact resistance tests on bamboo/plastic laminates.

Material	Number of Layers	Thickness (cm)	Drop Height k_0 (cm)	Absorbed Energy (Nm)
Bamboo/Epoxy	5	0.94	13.0	5.8
	8	1.00	15.0	6.6
Bamboo/Polylite	5	0.72	3.3	1.4
Bamboo/Urea Formaldehyde	5	0.60	7.8	3.4
	8	0.80	9.0	4.0

Relative bond strength can be analysed by comparing the energy absorbed during damage. Table 4 shows that epoxy and polylite matrix composites gave the upper and lower limiting strength and impact resistance respectively. Furthermore, thick specimens with more layers absorbed more impact energy due to the occurrence of interlaminar damage. The repetitive dropweight test with stepwise increases of energy is a cheap and reliable method for the ranking of materials.

TESTS FOR WATER ABSORPTION

As the water content of materials may affect bonding strength, stiffness and electrical properties, water absorptivity is an important consideration in the composite materials under study. The results of water absorptivity tests can be used to compare the suitability of different adhesives employed in this study.

Group B specimens of known dry weight were immersed in water for two days in a load-free state at room temperature (23°C). The results are presented in Table 5, which shows that epoxy ranked superior in water resistance, followed by urea formaldehyde and polylite.

Table 5. The water absorptivity of Group B bamboo/plastic composites.

Matrix Type	Water Absorbed % (by Weight)	Damage
Epoxy	6.0	No Cracks
Polylite	60.6	Serious Cracks
Urea Formaldehyde	25.3	Slightly Cracked

For Group A specimens, immersion time was 7 days. Since pure epoxy does not appreciably absorb water, it was concluded that the weight gain was due to uptake into the fibre-matrix interface and bamboo fibres and was more severe when laminae number increased. U.F. specimens absorbed 25.3% by weight of water, and was attributed to uptake in the matrix, interface and fibres. U.F. composites with added filler had a slightly lower absorptivity, as the filler hindered the entrance of water. During the initial stages of immersion, absorption was rapid, and reached a constant level after 7 days. The results

of our immersion test showed that epoxy matrix composites had higher water resistance than U.F. composites.

FIRE RESISTANCE TEST

Fire resistance has to be assessed if the bamboo/plastic composites are to be used as a timber substitute for structural purposes. Group B specimens made from all three kinds of matrices were subjected to flame tests. Specimens were 200 mm long, with two marks made 25 mm from each end. With the aid of a burner, the coupon specimen was kept burning until the first mark was reached. Then the burner was removed, and the nature of smoke emitted, as well as the persistence of the flame recorded.

Table 6 shows that U.F. composites burnt least easily, with no evolution of black smoke during burning. The flame extinguished spontaneously upon removal of the burner. Thus, they provide a high standard of safety.

Table 6. The results of flame tests on Group B bamboo/plastic specimens.

Matrix	Colour of Smoke	Time of Burning (min)	Self Extinction
Epoxy	Black	2.10	Yes
Polylite	Black	2.75	Yes
Urea Formaldehyde	Much Lighter	1.17	Yes

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper reports upon methods of fabricating bamboo fibre reinforced plastics by laying bamboo fibres in a mould with varying stack sequences, moulding pressure, temperature and curing time. If a suitable matrix is chosen, a composite of good strength can be obtained. Table 7 compares the test results of three kinds of matrices. Our data show that bamboo/epoxy has excellent mechanical properties, and is suitable for structural/construction work with stringent requirements. While the mechanical properties of bamboo/U.F. are only half as good as bamboo/epoxy, the matrix only costs 25% of epoxy, and is sufficiently useful in domestic situations.

Table 7. A summary of the properties of three kinds of bamboo/plastics of different matrices.

Tested Properties	Epoxy	Polylite	Urea Formaldehyde
Bending	Excellent	Bad	Good
Impact	Excellent	Bad	Good
Water Absorption	Excellent	Bad	Good
Fire Resistance	Good	Bad	Excellent

U.F. composites possess good flexural properties with low density. For [0] bamboo/epoxy and bamboo/U.F. laminates, the specific elastic modulus is roughly two times and 80% those of glass/epoxy (GRP) and mild steel respectively. However, this value decreases as laminae number increases. The flexural strength is comparable to mild steel and GRP. This value for [0/90] specimens of 5 or more laminae is only half that of [0] specimens, and is mainly due to the load sustained by longitudinal fibres. These characteristics are similar to other composites in general.

Water resistance and fire resistance of bamboo/U.F. is superior to wood. If BRP products are surface treated with epoxy, water resistance will be enhanced, while treatment with U.F. provides increased protection against

fires. These advantages allow for a wide scope of applications for this group of materials.

In conclusion, we suggest that BRP is a new type of light and strong material, which can be readily manufactured from a rich natural fibre resource at low cost, and provides sufficient mechanical properties and reasonable water and fire resistance. If future developments in manufacturing methodology allows improvement in fibre quality and bonding strength, their properties will be further enhanced. Thus, BRPs have immense potential to become a viable alternative to the expensive man-made fibre composites currently available, and a good substitute for timber.

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